

Brian Paul Kaess' Time as a Registrar at Gordon Tech High School

by Brian Paul Kaess

From November 30, 1998, to June 15, 2001—just over 2 ½ years—I worked as a high school Registrar at Gordon Tech Catholic High School on the north side of Chicago. Gordon, with an enrollment of 700 to 800 students, was a rival to my *alma mater*, Lane Tech High School, located nearby on Addison Avenue. However, while Lane was a selective public high school, Gordon was a private Catholic high school. Landing this job was like a scene out of 'Welcome Back Kotter.'

The principal, Casey Kozlik—a Lane graduate and an enlisted Air Force veteran of Vietnam— and Scott Dutton, the Assistant Principal, didn't seem to mind hiring Lane alumni. Lane was held in high regard in educational circles and considered a first choice for many Chicagoans. I felt I performed well during the interview and confidently answered the battery of questions posed to me. To my delight, one Sunday evening, Scott called to inform me I had been offered the job!

I began the next day in earnest. In the Records Office, our team consisted of a Registrar, a Scheduler, and a Records Clerk—all under my *aegis* or management. My team included Todd Schwager, George Bob, Mary Ann Nichols, and Marisol Santiago. During my tenure, we went through three different Schedulers. Gordon had a strong Polish presence among its faculty and staff, including Father Glab, Coach Wynecki, Tom Zbierski, and Kathy Kozebucki—and, as it happens, I am partly Polish myself. The student body was predominantly Hispanic, and we also had Hispanic faculty members. There was even an Italian element. Additionally, there were former Marines on staff, such as Coach Quanstrum and Coach Whelan. I still vividly recall Coach "Red" Miller's buoyant exclamation one day: "It's the best there ever was!" I believe he was thrilled to have a Marine in the Records Office—me.

Other faculty/staff members included Fred Kane, Ray Cipriano, Dr. Johann Rapp, Dennis Gaynor, Mrs. Laird, Nydia, Scott Baum, Mr. Tavano, Mr. Kurtz, Dave Kirk, Greg Vecchio, Father Malczyk, Titus Redman, Bob Derendal, Bob McKeon, Pam Mundy, Ms. Newlan, Dean Gui, Nydia, Jeanie, Donna and so on. One year, Cardinal George even came to visit the school and many of the faculty stood in line to shake or kiss his hand. The students were encouraged in their spirituality by Religion teachers, annual retreats, and school mass attendance. Todd Schwager converted because of his Polish Catholic wife. I married Mayte near Daley Plaza in a civil ceremony while I worked at G.T.

My role entailed a variety of tasks: distributing report cards and progress reports four times a year, stamping the Valedictorian and Salutatorian titles on diplomas, handing out diplomas to teachers during graduation at Holy Name Cathedral (who then distributed them to the students), calculating Grade Point Averages (GPA), creating and maintaining transcripts, issuing failure notices, processing alumni transcript requests (both official and unofficial), attending Open House, managing night school and summer school registration, preparing the *Office of Catholic Education* (OCE) report, evaluating transfer credits, proctoring distance education exams, and more! I even gave presentations on any updates in the Records Office to the school administrators in the Father Francis Gordon room. It felt like being in the *inner sanctum*.

Before one graduation, Todd Schwager and I even left the diplomas in a side room at Holy Name Cathedral and visited the Terra Museum of American Art just blocks away. Everybody needs a breadth of fresh air! George Bob was pretty conscientious as well about helping me secure the diplomas around Graduation time. .

I personally stamped and signed every transcript, worked with a scanner, and used three computers in the office. One of my responsibilities included preparing old alumni report cards for digitization. Additionally, I attended a Specialized Data Systems, Inc. workshop in Wheaton, Illinois, with George Bob. It was essential to stay sharp on the technical front, as the software occasionally inserted incorrect numbers into GPA calculations. Our team was constantly working to fine-tune the system.

One Sunday, I let my brother Garret visit the Records Office to use my computer for job-hunting. Apparently, he was very successful, landing a job at Eli Lilly, Inc. for over 20 years!

On my desk, I kept a photo of my Mexican wife Mayte, my Marine Corps photo, and a picture of myself with my ESL student, Victoria Brown—a beautiful Ukrainian woman. *Hej Sokoly* to that! I enjoyed eating ‘popcorn’ chicken in the cafeteria and heading over to subway’s for lunch. Food insecurity being a reality in America, not every kid at Gordon was that lucky. When I would come home late, Mayte would leave me dinner with cute ‘Bebe’ notes in Spanish.

I even ran into Tom Kleinschmidt, Gordon basketball legend and *alumni*, who had played in Japan, in the weight room. I played in the Student-Faculty basketball game and poured in a whopping 1 point on a free-throw. It must have been all those hacks! There was also an incident where Gordon students were caught smoking marijuana in the locker room, but I heard they only got a slap on the wrist. A Teacher named Darens was also led out by Chicago Police, ostensibly for molesting boys.

Gordon encouraged its staff to participate in extracurricular activities, and I served as the Assistant Coach of the Speech-and-Debate Team alongside Cindy Fey, the Head Coach. We traveled around Chicagoland in the Ram van, taking the team to debate meets at schools like Stevenson High School and Loyola Academy. We even made it to the Illinois Speech-and-Debate Finals, held in Springfield, where Cindy and I served as Finalist Judges. Hurray! We made it to Springfield!

I also briefly served as the Assistant Coach for the Chess Club, though my involvement was minimal. The Head Coach, a Serbian-American and CFD firefighter, led the team. While I was invited to coach basketball, the responsibilities of the Records Office left me with little time, and I had to decline. Nonetheless, Gordon helped partially reimburse me for adult computer classes I took at Truman College, leading me to earn a Basic Computer Literacy Certificate in 2001.

Additionally, I taught two sections of Freshman Literature—one during night school and another during the day. I thoroughly enjoyed teaching the students Shakespeare's *Hamlet* and *Romeo and Juliet* and even showed Films such as *Romeo & Juliet* (1968) & *Chariots of Fire* (1981). The former film starred the late Olivia Hussey and is considered a cinematic classic- one I pulled from the dusty shelves of the resource library of G.T.'s English Department! The night classes primarily consisted of public school students, while the day classes were exclusively Gordon students.

In 2001, I was let go due to grade reporting errors. When I was told I was fired, I left in a fit of *asperity*, but I can't say I didn't see it coming. Subsequently, I filed a complaint with the EEOC, as is standard procedure, when you're a disabled person who worked hard. I had near- perfect attendance. When I first arrived at the Records Office, it was in disarray and required extensive organization and cleanup. Once that was accomplished, I suspect they decided to let me go. In the end, I felt no bitterness towards the Archdiocese of Chicago, and was proud to have served, *albeit* for only for 2 ½ years, as a Catholic educator. Regardless, I moved on to my next "working stiff" job with somewhat less enthusiasm!

After Gordon, I worked as a Patient Service Representative III at Evanston Northwestern Healthcare in Skokie, Illinois, and as a part-time Computer Skills/ESL Instructor in Illinois Dist. 214 Adult Education at Randhurst Mall in Mt. Prospect, Illinois. I kept my third job at Truman College, teaching ESL on Saturdays. December 11, 2001 was the date when my son Paul Jesus Kaess was born at UIC Medical Center. Like my dad before me, at one point in my life, I worked three Jobs to support my family. Like the immigrant poet Seeger once said, 'But the land was sweet and good, and I did what I could.'